

Supplementary Materials: Synthesis and Characterization of Soluble Pyridinium Containing Copolyimides

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Figure S1. FTIR spectra of coPIs

Figure S2. FTIR spectra of coPI-Qs

Figure S3. NMR spectra of coPIs: DAP-0.2 (A), DAP-0.3 (B)

Figure S4. NMR spectra of coPI-Qs: DAP-0.2Q (A), DAP-0.3Q (B), DAP-0.2Q2-(C), DAP-0.3Q2 (D)